

Next-Generation Research Reactors: Novel Virginia Research and Education Reactor (VA-RER)

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1. ABSTRACT

The Virginia Research and Education Reactor (VA-RER) is a next-generation research reactor concept engineered to meet the urgent national need for modern, flexible, and AI-enabled modeling, design, operation and monitoring for diagnostics/prognostics. Built on the patented Test and Education Microreactor (TEM) architecture, the design integrates a central irradiation cavity, a neutron-spectrum-tailoring buffer zone, and a circular TRIGA-fuel lattice to support advanced applications in materials testing, isotope production, reactor physics research, and workforce development. The VA-RER is envisioned as a dual-reactor system, a zero-power unit dedicated to training and hands-on education, paired with a 5 to 10 MW_{th} reactor enabling high-flux irradiation experiments and validation of physics-based AI-driven digital-twin and autonomous monitoring technologies.

This paper presents preliminary neutronics analyses using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code system with ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data to evaluate the reactivity behavior of reactor configurations with irradiation cavity radii ranging from 6.25 cm to 100 cm. Five select core configurations are analyzed in this paper. The resulting eigenvalues range from 1.01581 to 1.06814, with reactivity gains diminishing for larger annular radii due to increased neutron leakage. Notably, an optimal moderator-to-fuel ratio emerges near a 25 cm radius, where the eigenvalue increases even with fewer total fuel rods. These findings provide early design guidance for maximizing irradiation volume while maintaining favorable neutronic performance, supporting ongoing development of a transformative research reactor for next-generation nuclear science and engineering.

Keywords: next generation research reactors, VA-RER design, TRIGA fuel, neutronics analysis, Monte Carlo, irradiation cavity

2. INTRODUCTION

U.S. research reactors have long served as essential platforms for nuclear science, engineering education, neutron activation analysis, neutron radiography, and materials testing. However, most existing facilities were constructed between the 1950s and 1970s and now face significant limitations due to aging infrastructure, constrained experimental environments, and insufficient instrumentation for high-fidelity measurements. As a result, their ability to support modern R&D needs is increasingly limited, including the validation of advanced multiphysics simulation tools, qualification of new fuels and structural materials, development and testing of physics-based AI-assisted monitoring and autonomous control systems, isotope production for medical and industrial applications, and comprehensive workforce development using digital twins and immersive visualization of multiphysics simulation results.

This paper introduces a novel research reactor concept based on a patented test and education microreactor (TEM) design [1]. The proposed design directly addresses the aforementioned gaps that current facilities either cannot meet or meet only with significant constraints. To effectively serve the full spectrum of emerging needs, the Virginia Research and Education Reactor (VA-RER) is envisioned as a dual-reactor system: a zero-power reactor dedicated to education and training, paired with a 5 to

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10 MW_{th} reactor focused on isotope production, materials testing, and the evaluation of advanced reactor technologies. The VA-RER embodies a transformative reactor concept designed to meet the nation's urgent need for modernized research and training infrastructure. By integrating advanced neutronics design, AI-enabled instrumentation, digital-twin technologies, and comprehensive educational and workforce development programs, the VA-RER positions Virginia at the forefront of the next era of nuclear innovation and capability.

The reactor design is intended to achieve high neutron flux and irradiation performance comparable to that of reactors fueled with highly enriched uranium (HEU, U-235 wt% $\geq 20\%$). For research reactors, two fully qualified low-enriched fuel types are currently available: TRIGA fuel and U₃Si₂ plate-type fuel, both enriched up to a maximum of 19.75 wt% U-235. In parallel, there are ongoing efforts to develop and deploy high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU) fuels, reflecting a U.S. national priority and building upon decades of experience converting research and test reactors worldwide from HEU to low-enriched fuel. However, the present study focuses exclusively on TRIGA fuel with an enrichment of 19.75 wt% U-235.

This paper presents preliminary excess reactivity calculations performed to evaluate the dimension and number of TRIGA fuel elements necessary to achieve criticality as a function of the irradiation cavity radius, with the goal of maximizing the space available to host experimental facilities (e.g., flow loops, large components) while minimizing the amount of fuel rods used.

3. OVERVIEW OF THE TEM ARCHITECTURE

The foundation of the TEM design, shown in *Figure 1. Schematic of the Virginia Research and Education Reactor (VA-RER)*. Figure 1, consists of a circular lattice core, a centrally located experimental cavity, and a buffer zone situated between the core and the cavity. The buffer zone serves two primary functions: (1) reducing feedback effects from the experimental cavity on the core, and (2) enabling neutron spectrum tailoring to achieve desired flux characteristics across energy ranges, such as those associated with fast or thermal reactor environments.

Figure 1. Schematic of the Virginia Research and Education Reactor (VA-RER).

The size of the experimental cavity directly influences its applicability for next-generation fuel and coolant experiments, isotope production, the number and configuration of fuel and control rods, and the overall accessibility and flexibility of the reactor design.

4. NEUTRONICS ANALYSIS OF ZERO-POWER VA-RER

In developing an optimized multi-purpose design, we established an initial set of objectives: achieving high neutron flux within the experimental cavity; accommodating a relatively large cavity radius; minimizing the reactivity feedback effects of the cavity on the reactor core; reducing the number of fuel pins while maintaining a long fuel cycle; and ensuring that fuel temperatures remain below acceptable limits under all operating conditions.

To meet these objectives, it is necessary to examine the sizes of the major components and their interrelationships. This paper presents a preliminary assessment of the three primary system components, the experimental cavity, the buffer zone, and the core region, and discusses their respective roles in achieving an integrated and effective reactor design.

Figure 2 presents the base model geometry developed for the VA-RER, which adopts an open-pool reactor configuration. Starting from the center and moving outward, the model consists of: a cavity with a radius of 100 cm; a buffer zone composed of three steel shells with a total thickness of 21 cm; a 5 cm-thick graphite reflector; a core arranged in three rings with 120 TRIGA-type fuel rods per ring; an additional 5 cm graphite reflector; a region housing the control drums; and the reactor vessel. In this conceptual model, standard TRIGA fuel elements are assumed, submerged in water as the moderating and cooling medium.

Figure 2. Preliminary OpenMC model of the VA-RER for analysis of the reactor cavity.

The axial and radial dimensions for the TRIGA fuel rods are shown in Figure 3 with color coded materials. Each fuel rod contains a central zirconium rod and an annular fuel region of uranium-zirconium hydride (U-ZrH) enriched to HALEU levels (19.75 U-235 wt. %), surrounded by a thin air gap and an outer stainless-steel cladding. Axially, there are graphite plugs and stainless-steel support structures on each end. The top of the fuel rod contains an air gap between the graphite plug and the support structure. At the bottom of the fuel rod, there is a very thin molybdenum disk separating the fuel from the graphite plug. The control drums surrounding the core have a diameter of 24 cm and are composed of two halves: a graphite reflector face (gray) and a B₄C absorber face (green). Axially, the control drums occupy the same active length as the fuel rods.

Figure 3. TRIGA fuel rod dimensions with colored coded materials: fuel (orange), Zr (purple), graphite (gray), stainless-steel (yellow), air (white), water (blue).

4. PRELIMINARY IRRADIATION CAVITY DIMENSION EVALUATION

In this study, five experimental cavity radii are considered: 6.25 cm, 12.5 cm, 25.0 cm, 50.0 cm, and 100.0 cm. For all cases, the buffer thickness is fixed at 21 cm, while the outer reactor dimensions are adjusted accordingly to accommodate the increased cavity size. For each cavity radius, configurations with 3 to 8 fuel rings were evaluated, maintaining an equal number of pins per ring within each configuration and enforcing a minimum allowable lattice pitch. From this parametric study, five representative reactor models were selected, corresponding to cavity radii of 6.25 cm, 12.5 cm, 25.0 cm, 50.0 cm, and 100.0 cm.

Using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code system [2] with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross-section and associated thermal scattering libraries provided by LANL, we performed eigenvalue simulations to determine the effective multiplication factor and the fission neutron distribution in each fuel rod, over 15 axial segments of 1-inch height. As an example, for the reactor model with a 100-cm cavity radius, Figure 4a shows the three-dimensional fission neutron distribution, while Figure 4b presents the corresponding statistical uncertainties. The fission distribution demonstrates the expected spatial behavior, with relative uncertainties on the order of $\pm 1\%$.

For purpose of demonstration, in this paper, we examine five cavity cases containing 8, 8, 5, 5, and 5 fuel rings, with 40, 48, 72, 104, and 168 pins per ring, respectively. Figure 5 shows the geometry of the five reactor models.

Table I summarizes the results of the five simulations, including the number of fuel rods per ring, the total number of rods for each configuration, and the corresponding eigenvalues, which range from $k = 1.01581$ to $k = 1.06814$ ($\Delta k = 5233$ pcm). Figure 6 illustrates the trend in the eigenvalues for these configurations.

As expected, increasing the number of fuel rings, and thus increasing the total fuel inventory, results in a corresponding rise in the reactor eigenvalue, ranging approximately from $k=1.01581$ to $k=1.06814$ ($\Delta k=5233$ pcm). It is also noteworthy that for larger cavity radii, the contribution of the outermost fuel rods diminishes due to enhanced neutron leakage, moderating the overall increase in reactivity. This effect becomes increasingly pronounced as the annular radius expands from 25.0 cm to 50.0 cm and from 50.0 cm to 100.0 cm. There also appears to be an optimal moderator-to-fuel ratio near an annular radius of 25.0 cm as evidenced by the fact that increasing the annular radius from 12.5 to 25.0 cm increased the system eigenvalue by 1448 pcm, despite the total number of fuel rods decreasing.

Figure 4. a, left) Fission source distribution in the VA-RER; b, right) Relative uncertainty of the fission source distribution in the VA-RER.

Table I. Comparison of k -eff vs. annular radius for VA-RER core configurations in Figure 5.

Annular Radius (cm)	Number of Rings	Number of Fuel Pins per Ring	Total Number of Fuel Rods	k -eff
6.25	8	40	320	1.01581±0.00015
12.5	8	48	384	1.03842±0.00014
25.0	5	72	360	1.05290±0.00014
50.0	5	104	520	1.06092±0.00011
100.0	5	168	840	1.06814±0.00009

Figure 5. Reactor models corresponding to cavity radii of 6.25 cm, 12.5 cm, 25.0 cm, 50.0 cm, and 100.0 cm.

Figure 6. Comparison of k_{eff} vs. annular radius for core configurations in Figure 5.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The VA-RER has a transformative reactor concept designed to meet the nation's urgent need for modernized research and training infrastructure. By integrating advanced neutronics design, AI-enabled instrumentation, digital-twin technologies, and comprehensive educational and workforce development programs, the VA-RER positions Virginia at the forefront of the next era of nuclear innovation and capability. The use of HALEU TRIGA fuel is well-aligned and will benefit from the US interest in rapidly developing an HALEU production pipeline. HALEU fuel will also allow to obtain reactor performances comparable to those of equivalent high-power HEU test reactors.

To maximize the amount of irradiation space available to host experiments and samples, the neutronics design has been initiated by evaluating the excess reactivity of different configurations with variable cavity radii. The results show that increasing the radii of the annular cavity reduces the rate in which the eigenvalue increases. Beyond an annular radius of 25.0 cm, the contribution of additional fuel rods to the eigenvalue decreases significantly. Within the vicinity of 25.0 cm, there appears to be an optimal configuration as eigenvalue increases despite a decrease in total fuel rods in the core. This suggests efforts should be focused on annular radii of this size to further narrow the scope of our design.

Extensive analysis of the reactor design, materials, dimensions, and buffer zone to the reactor cavity are under analysis with the goal to maximize the irradiation volume and neutron flux available for irradiation of large experiments (e.g., large molten salt loops) and of samples (e.g., for production of radioisotopes). Further analysis is being performed to determine the effects of the control drums to help design an effective control system.

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